

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D4.4

SYNTHESIS REPORT OF TRAINING AND PEER LEARNING EFFORTS

Summary:

This document is a synthesis report of the training and peer learning efforts of the SUMEX project including the Massive Open Online Course, the Community of Practice and the Knowledge Repository.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
2	THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A LEARNERS AND LEADERS LEAGUE (3L).....	5
3	COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE	6
3.1	SETUP, INITIATION AND FOLLOW-UP.....	6
3.2	SUMEX CONSORTIUM PARTNERS AND EXPERTS	7
3.3	MOOC PARTICIPANTS	8
3.4	OTHER PARTICIPANTS	8
4	WHAT ARE THE SUMEX 3L ACTIONS?.....	9
4.1	MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSE	9
4.2	LINKEDIN GROUP	15
4.3	REPOSITORY.....	15
5	MEASURED IMPACT OF THE 3L ACTIONS.....	17
5.1	MOOC AND REPOSITORY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS.....	17
5.2	MOOC SURVEY.....	18
5.3	MOOC ANECDOTAL EVIDENCE ANALYSIS.....	19
6	CONCLUSION.....	21
6.1	LESSONS LEARNT IN SUMEX	21
6.2	RECOMMENDATIONS IN PEER LEARNING AND TRAINING SETTINGS	22
6.3	NEXT STEPS: EIT ACADEMY FOR MOOC & COP CONTINUATION	23

FIGURES

Figure 1:	Screenshot from the SUMEX CoP on LinkedIn	6
Figure 2:	SUMEX MOOC on the Future Learn platform	9
Figure 3:	Exemplary designated discussion steps in the MOOC Week one and designated article step (1.4) ...	10
Figure 4:	Screenshot of excerpt of an interactive critical discussion on the MOOC	11
Figure 5:	Screenshot of excerpt of participant inputs on other practice examples on the MOOC	12
Figure 6:	Screenshots of excerpt of participant questions and lead educator response on the MOOC	14
Figure 7:	The SUMEX knowledge repository.....	16
Figure 8:	"Submit a Practice" feature.....	16
Figure 9:	MOOC first live run distribution of participants.....	17
Figure 10:	MOOC second live run distribution of participants.....	18
Figure 11:	Exemplary discussion step from MOOC week one.....	20

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The extractive sector's site-specific nature, the diversity of institutional settings across different EU Member States, and the frequent conflicts of interest between businesses and civil society make establishing a consistent, trustworthy, and inclusive Community of Practice (CoP) a challenging task. In light of these challenges, the SUMEX project strategically positioned the formation of a Community of Practice (CoP) and accompanying peer-learning and training activities as a core objective. The SUMEX project, conceptualised as an extractives sector Coordination and Support Action (CSA), has at its core a community of practitioners willing to engage in a sustainable development transition in the extractives sector. This report summarises the SUMEX approach to a Community of Practice (CoP) as well as the Learners and Leaders League (3L) with regards to its purpose, relevant SUMEX actions, benefits and next steps.

This report provides an overview of the SUMEX approach to building a Community of Practice (CoP) and the Learners and Leaders League (3L), encompassing their purposes, relevant SUMEX actions, associated benefits, and future steps. At its centre, the SUMEX project established 3L as its approach to identify, categorise, recruit and involve people and organisations in important training and learning activities. While the physical and in-person component of education, learning and training is important (e.g. regional peer-learning workshops), the project's activities around the SUMEX Toolkit focuses on the online and digital component. The SUMEX Toolkit representing a central and dynamic tool of good practices and principles consists of an online repository as well as a massive open online course (MOOC). All digital learning and training activities (SUMEX Toolkit and LinkedIn Group) of the CoP and 3L have been built around and in parallel to it (e.g. CoP Members where incremental in identifying real world practices for the repository component while selected practices have been utilised as good practice examples in the MOOC). Against this background, chapters two, three and four provide an overview about CoP and 3L setup, detailing the actions and benefits accrued from learning and training activities.

Concludingly, we summarise the key lessons learnt during the process of Community of Practice (CoP) formation and post-project sustainability, and how they relate to the design and implementation of SUMEX 3L actions:

- 1) **Carefully planning and time allocation for CoP formation:** It is difficult initiating and sustaining discussions within the CoP. Even though performance indicators were achieved, getting CoP members to actively engage in 3L actions proved to be a challenge.
- 2) **Leveraging in-person meetings and existing networks facilitate for digital engagement:** Trust and established relationships are an important precondition for people to interact digitally.
- 3) **Online environments during the Pandemic as an appropriate response:** Shifting topical discussions online and the feasibility of learning asynchronous, made the approach of using an online course format, albeit it being necessary by the COVID-19 crisis, a good and sustainable decision.
- 4) **Integrating real-time interaction with asynchronous learning:** The blend of text materials, examples sourced from the repository, real-time interaction on discussion forums, expert videos, and quizzes, worked effectively to engage the CoP.

As a result of the in-depth and comprehensive stock-taking of CoP and 3L actions, the SUMEX project proposed recommendations for future digital learning and training efforts (see chapter 5.2).

2 THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A LEARNERS AND LEADERS LEAGUE (3L)

The SUMEX project, conceptualised as an extractives sector community support and coordination project, has at its core a community of practitioners willing to engage in a sustainable development transition in the extractives sector. This report provides an overview of the SUMEX approach to building a Community of Practice (CoP) and the Learners and Leaders League (3L), encompassing their purposes, relevant SUMEX actions, associated benefits, and future steps.

The SUMEX project developed a digital toolkit, working as a central and dynamic knowledge repository of good practices and principles consisting of an online repository as well as a massive open online course (MOOC). It is intended to serve as the foundation for learning and capacity-building processes within the CoP, with a vision of its self-sustainability extending beyond the duration of SUMEX.

Due to the very contextual and site-specific nature of extractive sector practices, the differentiated and diverse institutional settings in different EU Member States, oftentimes conflictual nature of business interests and civil society engagement, makes forming a consistent, trustful and inclusive CoP a challenging task for the extractives sector. A CoP is a group of people and organisations that collaborate to find innovative solutions for complex problems such as in the case for sustainable extractive sector practices in the public and private sector.

While all target audiences will benefit from SUMEX actions, a select group of individuals and organizations, specifically the 3L and CoP members, will gain deeper insights from the project's comprehensive and informal learning and engagement components. Within the context of sustainability transitions, everyone is viewed as both a Learner and Leader. In this framework, the 3L serves as a collective of people and organizations committed to incentivizing and facilitating the formation of a CoP and driving the transformation toward a sustainable extractive sector. The CoP, and particularly the 3L, play a pivotal role in shaping and executing both the SUMEX Toolkit repository and the learning component (WP4), as well as the physical learning and exchange processes (WP5).

Central to the formation and establishment of the 3L and CoP are project actions targeting the exchange of knowledge among its members which in SUMEX is referred to as peer-to-peer learning. The peer learning approach is based on personal interactions among peers on physical and online platforms to enable a global exchange of use cases and peer-to-peer experiences.

In the context of the SUMEX Toolkit, the CoP members represent the entirety of people and organisations benefitting from 1) SUMEX 3L actions as well as 2) accompanying educational, learning and training materials. For example, we used the CoP to keep the discussion from the dissemination workshop we organised at the World Resources Forum in Geneva going by transferring questions posted from online participants in the CoP on the LinkedIn Group (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Screenshot from the SUMEX CoP on LinkedIn

3 COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The SUMEX project is structured as a networking, dialogue-enabling and capacity building platform and has at its core the goal to enable and foster existing dialogues and generate new ones in the extractives sector. For this, the project needs a community of practitioners willing to engage in a sustainable development transition in the extractives sector. This Community of Practice (CoP) forms the base for guiding future decision making and implementation of practices fostering a sustainable sector in both policy and industry.

For the purpose of engaging with people and organisations with similar learning needs and organisational backgrounds as well as to narrow down the thematic focus, SUMEX will engage 3L and CoP members along the five SUMEX Focus Areas (FAs), i.e. socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting, and permitting.

3.1 SETUP, INITIATION AND FOLLOW-UP

The definition of the core goals of the CoP is crucial to map out the targeted audience, the formation of the members, and the chosen learning approaches. A thorough process is necessary to create a sustainable community that keeps the dialogue going even after project end and ultimately enables a more sustainable extractives sector. Therefore, careful consideration is given to the selection, recruitment and engagement with potential members of the 3L community and a careful mapping process was done before setting up the community (see D6.5 EU extractive industry mapped key stakeholders).

The CoP plays a fundamental role in the design of the SUMEX Toolkit (mainly the knowledge repository and the MOOC). For the mapping of the members, the SUMEX project drew on extensive networks: partner organisations or informal networks and multiplier organisations such as business associations (e.g. UEPG) or official platform networks (e.g. informal network of mining authorities) or via past project networks (i.e. H2020 Project MIN-GUIDE National Focal Points, NFPs i.e. public administrators working on mineral policy design in EU

MS; or H2020 INTRAW project and its later instigation of the International Raw Material Observatory and its Board of Members). The members are further elaborated on the following chapters.

The extractives sector is heavily influenced by industry stakeholder actions; however, many other parties are affected by these actions and play an influential role in defining and shaping the sustainability agenda in the extractives industry. Governments and public authorities play an ever-increasing role in shaping rules that guide behaviours of. At the same time civil society organisations, and, in particular, environmental NGOs and citizens groups, continue to play an ever-important role in the industry performance towards more sustainable practices or highlighting problematic approaches and practices. This is why the 3L and CoP span industry, civil society, as well as policy members around the globe.

In the context of the SUMEX Toolkit, the CoP members represent the entirety of people and organisations benefitting from 1) SUMEX 3L actions as well as 2) accompanying educational, learning and training materials. SUMEX Toolkit (WP4) and Peer learning actions (WP5) which are collectively referred to as 3L actions, are designed to target CoP members through various initiatives.

3.2 SUMEX CONSORTIUM PARTNERS AND EXPERTS

The leaders and learners league (3L) were set up following a thorough process and consists of the SUMEX consortium partners, the MOOC participants as well as the members of the SUMEX LinkedIn group. The 3L forms the more focused learning and training activities (3L activities; i.e. MOOC or LinkedIn Group) within the wider CoP.

External experts were consulted by the SUMEX consortium partners during different peer-learning and knowledge exchange activities. These included webinars, regional workshops, expert-stakeholder interviews, audio-visual storytelling interviews, and discussions in online for a like the LinkedIn group.

The experts and the consortium identified relevant case studies and reached out to their networks. These case studies were mapped and assessed to predefined criteria by the consortium and the experts and then formed the foundation of the SUMEX knowledge repository as well as the main input for the MOOC. Once the desired level of community involvement has been reached, the consortium's responsibilities shifted towards editing and moderating interactions. As community moderators, the consortium members monitor membership levels, design, run and review interactions in the MOOC and the LinkedIn group.

They defined experts and leaders were involved in the regional peer-learning workshops as well in the Brussels workshop as presenters, panellists and supporter of the events. The experts in the 3L were presenters of good practice cases, panellists coming from different regions and different actor groups as well as supporters of the workshops.

Additional activities for engaging the CoP included:

- [Webinars](#): Good practice and peer learning webinars were organised throughout the project.
- [Webcasts](#): YouTube Recordings of e.g. webinars and project activities were made available for on-demand viewing throughout, and beyond the project's lifetime.
- [Expert-stakeholder video interviews](#): Videos of interviews with experts, focusing on different aspects of the project in the targeted sector contribute to creating wider engagement, understanding and accessibility of SUMEX to a wider audience.
- [AV story telling videos](#): Videos for each focus area constitute a prime vehicle for combining information and graphics to disseminate SUMEX results in an attractive, barrier-free format to a wider audience and form the core of the weekly steps of the MOOC.

- [Online discussion fora](#): The digital platform will provide opportunities for stakeholders to discuss and exchange information in an online forum, the SUMEX LinkedIn group as well as designated discussion steps in each knowledge step in the MOOC.
- [Podcast](#): as of October 2023, six episodes of the podcast were published and made available on the SUMEX website: <https://www.sumexproject.eu/2023/05/03/sumex-podcast/>. The Podcast was utilised to disseminate SUMEX results in an attractive, barrier-free format to a wider audience.

3.3 MOOC PARTICIPANTS

It is important for the 3L to include people who benefit from the research and the findings of the project. This opens up feedback channels and ensures the applicability of the results while simultaneously opening the communication channels to a wider network of stakeholders.

As can be seen in more detail in the following chapter, the MOOC participants came from all around the world, spanning all stakeholder groups: industry, civil society, and policy. With the possibility to discuss every step of the course with each other as well as with respective experts during the two live-runs, participants were actively involved in the 3L and were given the possibility to connect with each other and the experts.

For this purpose, webinar and interview recordings were used in each expert week in the course, introducing the learners to area experts and showing different perspectives on the respective topics. The experts from the webinars and interviews were also included as leaders in the 3L and consulted for other 3L activities as well as regional and digital workshops and events.

3.4 OTHER PARTICIPANTS

In addition to the MOOC participants and the SUMEX experts, other participants form a wide base of the 3L and CoP. These include members of the SUMEX LinkedIn group, the subscribers of the newsletter, as well as the listeners of the SUMEX podcast.

The SUMEX newsletter was sent out on a regular basis and around 240 people are subscribed and engage with the content. The newsletter was used to inform interested parties about the SUMEX project, the project and research results, the toolkit, as well as interesting upcoming events.

The SUMEX podcast, launched in May 2023 encompasses six episodes covering the introduction to the project and podcast and an episode for each focus area. The episodes are hosted on the platform *Pod Bean*. The podcast page has been visited around 450 times and 188 downloads (status: 15 October 2023) were registered via [Pod Bean](#). With these activities as well, all stakeholder groups were represented in each of the activities, making sure that the project is applicable and used by the whole community and that the CoP is actively engaged and informed.

4 WHAT ARE THE SUMEX 3L ACTIONS?

The SUMEX Project divided its 3L actions into three main parts: a massive open online course (MOOC) on the Future Learn platform, a community of practice engaging on LinkedIn in a special group, and the creation and maintenance of a repository of case studies on the SUMEX website, all aiming to enable and inform the CoP.

The following chapters present these three taken measures.

4.1 MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSE

The SUMEX MOOC hosted on the Future Learn platform consists of a six Week course spanning an introductory week and the five SUMEX focus areas - impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, permitting, and reporting. After an introduction to the topic, the participants are presented with expert insights, real life examples and an assignment finishing the week off. The MOOC can be completed by online participation and approximately 2 hours of study per week.

Sustainable Management in the Extractive Industry

Explore the importance of sustainability in the extractive industry and what the solutions along 5 key action areas are

850 enrolled on this course

- **Duration**
6 weeks
- **Weekly study**
2 hours
- **100% online**
[How it works](#)
- **Unlimited subscription**
~~€299.99~~ €209.99 for one year
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Sustainable Management in the Extractive Industry

850 enrolled on this course

- 6 weeks
- 2 hours per week
- Digital certificate when eligible
- Advanced level

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Figure 2: SUMEX MOOC on the Future Learn platform

After completing the course, participants are able to

- Reflect on the importance of a coherent approach to sustainability framework in the extractive sector,
- Explain the societal relevance of raw material extraction,
- Investigate the main pillars of sustainable extractive management,
- Apply sustainability frameworks for mineral extraction to different institutional and local contexts,
- Identify and evaluate good practices in the extractive industry in a critical manner,
- Discuss with experts and peers the current state and related challenges of the European extractive sector,
- Explore the SUMEX tools and others about good practice learning.

Welcome to the course

In this first activity, we welcome you to the MOOC on 'Sustainable Management in the Extractive Industry'. We will introduce relevant topics and provide an overview of the coming weeks. We are excited to have you on board.

1.1 Introduction to the course VIDEO (08:19)

1.2 Meet the team ARTICLE

1.3 Get to know each other DISCUSSION

The European perspective

Gain an overview of the EU policy landscape for the extractive sector and discuss current issues and challenges of the sector.

1.4 Current issues and challenges in mineral extraction ARTICLE

1.5 An EU policy landscape ARTICLE

1.6 Discussion on the European perspective DISCUSSION

The many facets of sustainability

Get insights into the different lenses through which the SUMEX project approaches the analysis of sustainability in the extractive sector, these include the concepts of Leverage Points and the Institutional Resource Regime (IRR).

1.7 The SUMEX approach to sustainability in the extractives sector ARTICLE

1.8 Tensions and trade-offs illustrated in three SUMEX sustainability aspects and how to resolve them ARTICLE

1.9 Sustainability concepts for assessing extractive sector practices ARTICLE

1.10 Discussion on sustainability in the extractive sector DISCUSSION

Current issues and challenges in mineral extraction

8 comments

In the extractives sector, both the policy and industry efforts have gone a long way to improve environmental performance, increase trust towards local community and society overall, and satisfy raw material needs of downstream sectors. Still, challenges remain on various fronts.

Environmental Challenge

Mineral extraction is still a very land, energy and waste intensive activity, with a plethora of potential negative consequences for the environment if not adequately managed. For example, new extractive projects and the sector as a whole need to increase efforts along several lines:

- To counteract the destruction of biodiversity and ecosystems, accountable land management and rehabilitation plans need to be implemented.
- To avoid pollution of the local environment and water bodies, all waste streams, including tailings need to be properly managed.
- To further reduce related GHG emissions, energy efficiency and the electrification of extractive activities with renewable energies need to be pursued further.

Local Benefit & Societal Contract Challenge

The extractive sector in Europe enjoys a greater degree of acceptance compared to other world regions, due to the levels of trust in public administration and their role in prioritizing the

Figure 3: Exemplary designated discussion steps in the MOOC Week one and designated article step (1.4)

To actively engage with the learners, the course was designed with two live-runs, the first one in November 2022 and the second one in August 2023. During these live runs, each week of the course is hosted by the focus area expert. These experts actively participate by interacting with the participants in the comments section, addressing questions, and encouraging discussions among the learners.

Stimulating critical discussions among participants:

The MOOC provides interesting perspectives along a variety of topics (i.e. “issues in the extractive industry that cannot be properly addressed with Impact Assessment?”) to initiate critical discussions (i.e. how to resolve negative impacts of mining, such as, for example, via a national mineral policy) among its participants. Against this background, the MOOC provides participants to share ideas and concerns on topics based on their professional background and training (mining consultants, development experts) and the geographical origin of where the problem or issue is situated (development country or mining country origin in Europe or other parts of the world). Thus, it allows for testing different paradigms (private vs. public intervention) in very specific contexts (private sector social benefit programmes or national revenues shared for mining regions).

Figure 4: Screenshot of excerpt of an interactive critical discussion on the MOOC

Ways to collect additional ideas & inputs from participants:

Some ways to engage with participants on e-learning formats such as the MOOC are asking about their own work and real-life examples or about what they heard that interested or sparked their attention (i.e. “In this step we ask you tell us about a practice which you find interesting, which is related to impact assessment (either something you have come across in your careers or search for an interesting practice online)”). This is not only a useful way to facilitate interesting discussions, but also highlights that participants are knowledgeable on their own and can provide important inputs for lessons learnt beyond what is provided in the MOOC content material (e.g. by posting videos, sharing articles or just their experience on a practice).

NM
Follow
30 AUG

The challenge of measuring the impacts on migratory pathways is of interest. There are multiple variables to be considered in geographies that the mine/project has not impact upon. It is therefore difficult to measure the causes and effects because the mine site is a small component along a migration pathway. The solution is to consider migratory species through transnational databases. This can identify where the pressures are and the potential for the mine/project site to be a potential positive location by reducing stress on the species. The target audience would be bird NGOs.

 Pin
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[Profile]
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26 AUG

Reclamation project in a huge coal mining area in Iowa, USA. Mining operations happened more than 40 years ago when there were no impact assessments at all.

<https://youtu.be/V5AJMz67KBg?si=AJAVzIC6GnNwJmE3>

Restoration of this area has been a very slow process, but the initial steps taken are showing to the communities that it is possible to recover the soil productivity. The water flows are still in bad conditions with few exceptions. It is very interesting to see the progress.

(edited)

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JC
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23 AUG

The post-closure management of the Lisheen Mine in Ireland, A major underground Zinc mine in the Irish midlands closed in 2016, the tailings dam has now been sealed and is being returned to agricultural use, the mine built a wind farm on the site during the operation which continues to provide clean energy to the local area. The site is now home to a bio-economy research centre and in most ways the local area has benefited environmentally and socially from the mine both during its operation and after its closure. This is in stark contrast to some of Ireland's historic mine sites. Lisheen provides an example of best practice which can be referenced in future projects.

 Pin
 Like 2
 Reply
 Bookmark
 Report

KC
Follow
23 AUG

A coal mining getting restored in INDIA

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X7H7jweDRh0>

Figure 5: Screenshot of excerpt of participant inputs on other practice examples on the MOOC

Be an active facilitator during the MOOC live-run time

Throughout the MOOC running time, SUMEX project experts (i.e. lead educators) were asked to actively facilitate discussions, ask questions, and provide stimulating questions for discussions. To be active during the MOOC running time, is an important driver for stimulating discussions and make people feel heard in their concerns. Coordination and detailed briefings are necessary to prepare Lead Educators on their task and keep people interested and active in discussions.

KC **Course team replied** Follow 11 SEP

Permitting has many challenges, the key ones are

1. Contradictory with the extraction process of minerals
2. Complex and time consuming, monetary costs are involved
3. Too many stakeholders (departments) involved, all have their own motives, so reaching consensus is really tricky
4. The precursor to permitting process, the environmental and biodiversity assessment is mostly reactively done (not pro-actively done barring some countries), hence it lacks genuine intent to protect, looks more as a forced process i.e., "doing it because law forces it otherwise would have been skipped"

 Pin
 Liked 2
 Reply
 Bookmark
 Report

[Mute this conversation](#)

 Andreas Endl **Lead Educator** 18 SEP

Dear Kaushik,

Thanks for your comments. Maybe you could clarify or explicate a bit more on :

ad 1: Why contradictory?

ad 3: i.e. on political - administrative level or public level (i.e. consultations with public / FPIC)

ad 4: yes indeed, much that has been enforced by law becomes a minimum requirements. However, there are also front runner companies and practice examples who try to go beyond (i.e. net positive impact on biodiversity examples in the LIFE project; and see the example at the end of this week)

 Like 1
 Reply
 Bookmark
 Edit

 Course team replied Follow 01 SEP

The discussion is very inspiring. It reminds me of another important issue concerning multinational companies. As long as local authorities do not have enough knowledge for mining sustainable development, do they tend to offer higher prices for upcoming multinational companies? Because doing so may help compensate their potential loss due to the uncertainties. But too high rental and too much requirements for developers are not good as well.

 Report

 Michael Tost Lead Educator Follow 04 SEP

Dear , this should not be an issue in the EU from a legal perspective. However, it might be relevant for social acceptance (SLO), as communities / people generally have higher expectations for multinationals.

 Report

SB **Course team replied** Follow 29 AUG

As this course focuses on the extractive industry, I note that the entire focus of the Land Use planning process is on development of land with apparently little or no consideration on the possibility of non-development of land, i.e. deliberately choosing not to develop land (or to let it become rewilded) whether as national parks or other non-development areas. While it might be implicit that the non-development of land is an option, it is not included in the previous discussion. If it was, I suspect that our industries' reasonable response would be that given a suitably robust remediation process, post-extraction, a broadly similar environmental result could be achieved in the long term as with non-development (or at least one that balances the need for extraction with the natural environment).
(edited)

 Report

 Besmira Dyca Lead Educator Follow 30 AUG

Thanks for the comment Stephen! Indeed, extractives vs. conservation discussion is equally important. You might find interesting inputs on this in the expert discussion, as well as in the case presented in section 3.8 on metal mining and reindeer herding (the latter relying on preserved pasture land for its subsistence).

I agree that it is important to consider the temporality of mining as a land use. But also the timing and enforcement of post-mining rehabilitation plans is crucial as unfortunately sometimes post-mining can look different from rehabilitation plans on paper. At the same time, considerations on how renewable resources are affected during the mining operation should also be factored in in the land use planning decision, and that's why EIA and land use planning should go hand in hand, not one as an afterthought of the other.

 Report

Figure 6: Screenshots of excerpt of participant questions and lead educator response on the MOOC

As of October 2023, the MOOC counts over 850 enrolments.

The MOOC is available under the following link: <https://bit.ly/SUMEXMOOC>

After project end, the course will be transferred to EIT Raw Materials (More on this in chapter 5.3).

4.2 LINKEDIN GROUP

Creating space for the dialogue in the mineral extraction community is an important step to keep the conversation going. Within the SUMEX project, a LinkedIn group was created in October 2022 to keep interested parties informed about the progress of the project, to enable access to project outputs like reports, podcasts and upcoming events, as well as to create a base for exchange between the stakeholders. As such the LinkedIn Group forms an important part of the SUMEX CoP.

Regular updates are posted within the group by the project consortium to keep members informed about the latest developments. Additionally, members have the opportunity to engage in conversations with each other by sharing updates on current events, publications, or general questions. This active exchange of information and ideas fosters a dynamic and collaborative environment within the group.

As of October 2023, the group counts over 200 members. The LinkedIn group is available under the following link: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/14134912/>

After the project end, the CoP will be transferred to the EU project CIRAN, with the idea being to broaden the CoP to other EU projects with similar scopes to SUMEX. More on this in chapter 5.3.

4.3 REPOSITORY

The extractives sector is a worldwide spanning industry, consolidating the information and knowledge is thus crucial to enable exchange between all stakeholders. The SUMEX knowledge repository does exactly this: the presented use cases and best practices cover examples from the whole world and give interested parties the opportunity to inform themselves and learn about real-life examples.

The repository is designed to offer easy and fast access to relevant data and a basis to define the discourse in the 3L, like what is the current sector performance, where are gaps, where are good/disruptive practices, etc. The platform makes it possible to sort by year, the five SUMEX focus areas, by practice type, extractive life-cycle, sustainability scope, and other factors. It not only covers industry practices, but also presents civil society as well as policy actions.

Currently, the repository has 370 data items. With the new feature to “[submit a practice](#)” online form, interested parties can submit their own use cases.

The repository is available under the following link: <https://repository.sumexproject.eu/>

SUMEX TOOLKIT

Knowledge repository

Your open access to knowledge on how to change the extractive sector towards sustainability. Navigate through the industry- and policy practices, training materials, reports, and much more.

[Submit a practice](#)

Enter any search text and/or use the filters below

[Search](#)

SUMEX repository | 370 Results

Sort by ▾

FILTERS [More info & Meta-data](#)

- YEAR ▾
- SUMEX FOCUS AREA ▾
- PRACTICE TYPE ▾
- EXTRACTIVE LIFE-CYCLE ▾

KNOWLEDGE BASE

RIOTINTO'S CLOSURE PLANNING

Every Rio Tinto-managed operation must have a robust closure plan in place. For uniformity in closure planning and management, a comprehensive Closure standard is applied to all of their activities. Additionally, it aids in identifying chances for their actions to have beneficial socioeconomic effects.

PRACTICE BASE

Figure 7: The SUMEX knowledge repository

SUMEX: Submit a new practice to our Knowledge Repository

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

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SUMEX TOOLKIT

Knowledge repository

Your open access to knowledge on how to change the extractive sector towards sustainability. Navigate through the industry- and policy practices, training materials, reports, and much more.

The SUMEX project is continuously looking for new practices in the extractive sector that push the boundaries of what is possible on sustainable management.

In case you would like to highlight any SUMEX-relevant practices, please send us the following information via the submission form below (see our quality criteria here):

Please provide some basic information on the following questions:

* What is the concrete practice about and which are the main organisations implementing it? (Example: a social engagement process with local community members on the expansion of an existing extractive project?)

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Figure 8: "Submit a Practice" feature

5 MEASURED IMPACT OF THE 3L ACTIONS

Measuring the impact of the 3L actions in the day-to-day business life of the community of practitioners is not possible. However, some performance indicators and surveys were implemented to gain insight into the general opinion of the CoP on the 3L actions and their impacts. These mainly include statistics from the MOOC, video views, and various survey results.

5.1 MOOC AND REPOSITORY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The SUMEX MOOC was hosted on the Future Learn platform, which offers a variety of indicators regarding the participants of the course. However, it is important to note that participation in these indicators is not mandatory for all course participants, which can lead to variations in enrolment numbers.

The first live run in November 2022 had 405 participants from around the world (see picture below). These learners visited the MOOC training steps 5043 times. Not only were all continents covered within the participant distribution, but all stakeholder groups were represented.

Figure 9: MOOC first live run distribution of participants

In the second live run held in August 2023, there were 386 participants, and the MOOC training steps were visited a total of 2,580 times. Similar to the first run, participants from all continents and various stakeholder groups were actively engaged in the course. It's important to note that the variation in the number of participants and steps visited in the second run is due to the differing accessibility duration of the course at the time of this report.

Figure 10: MOOC second live run distribution of participants

As mentioned before, the MOOC is divided into six weeks. Each week has an introduction to the topic and/or a recording of an expert discussion on the topics. These videos were viewed over 800 times (as per October 2023). In addition, the project has created more videos and recordings for dissemination purposes.

The repository spans 370 real-life use cases spanning all five focus areas and extractive lifecycle stages. The repository website section on the SUMEX project website was viewed 5225 times since the launch.

5.2 MOOC SURVEY

A survey was set up by EFG to measure the perceived impact of the MOOC on learners' site. For this, five questions were asked:

- Which extractive sector stakeholder group do you belong to?
- Do you think the Massive Open Online Course improved your understanding & awareness of the challenges related to sustainable management in the extractives sector?
- Do you think the Massive Open Online Course will have a positive impact on your attitude towards implementing sustainable management practices?
- How likely will you increase your contact and engagement with sustainability practitioners in the extractive sector after the MOOC?
- What topics did you miss in order to improve sustainable management in the extractive sector (briefly elaborate why)?

Participants were able to respond to questions two to four on a scale from "1 to 5", "1" being no impact/improvement and "5" being high impact/improvement.

The average response to question two, the improvement of understanding and awareness of challenges related to sustainable management, was a rating of four, indicating a high improvement on the learners' site.

The average rating for question three, impact on implementing sustainable practices, was a little over four, also indicating a high impact on the learners' day-to-day practices.

Lastly, the average rating of question four, increasing contact and engagement with the CoP, was a four, again indicating a highly likely continuous contact within the CoP.

DELIVERABLE 4.4

75% of respondents have a background in research and academia, while the other 25% come from industry. No policy authorities were represented in the survey.

5.3 MOOC ANECDOTAL EVIDENCE ANALYSIS

As mentioned above, participants of the MOOC had the opportunity to exchange knowledge, opinions, and information for each step of the course. Each subject was designed with a designated step for a discussion, providing specific questions to be answered related to the content of the week. In addition, participants had the possibility to comment on each step of the course, ask questions to the lead educators and engage with their fellow learners. On average, the comments on the steps averaged from 5 to 35 comments over both courses runs.

In a summative descriptive analysis, the SUMEX course team analysed the comments in both MOOC live-runs. The analysis looked into aspects of 1) what people found interesting (e.g. safety culture in mining companies), 2) what practical examples did they mention and whether SUMEX could utilise these in its own research or feeding it into the knowledge repository (e.g. new reports, hyperlinks or videos on other practices), 3) what was the background of people (e.g. mining consulting) for identifying the stakeholder group origin of participants

VC **Valentina Cetean** **Follow** 07 SEP

I consider the Management of waste from extractive industries became the most important legislative document, taking into account not only the mandatory steps for a circular economy, but also the need to ensure the sustainability of every human action.

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 Abdolsattar Roudini **Follow** 31 AUG

Among the various EU policies, three stand out in their impact on the extractive sector: the Environmental Impact Assessment Directive, the Extractive Waste Directive, and the Water Framework Directive.

Environmental Impact Assessment Directive: This policy ensures that before any mining project starts, its potential impact on the environment is carefully assessed. It's like a green light that prompts miners to think about the environment and plan for its protection right from the beginning.

Extractive Waste Directive: This one's about managing waste from mining responsibly. It's like making sure that we clean up after ourselves, preventing any accidents, and taking care of the land we use.

Water Framework Directive: Imagine a rulebook for using water sustainably. With mining needing lots of water, this directive guides how water is used, so we don't harm the environment or communities that depend on water.

In short, these policies shape how mining happens, from considering the environment's health to managing waste and using water wisely. It's like having rules in place to ensure we're being responsible stewards of the Earth while extracting resources.

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JC **John Conneally** Course team replied **Follow** 14 AUG

The EU environmental impact assessment directive is likely one of the most important EU policies for the extractive industry. While other pieces of EU legislation are also directly applicable to the industry this directive provides an overarching framework covering all of the other aspects of EU policy and requires operations to comprehensively assess the environmental impacts of their activities.

Figure 11: Exemplary discussion step from MOOC week one

6 CONCLUSION

6.1 LESSONS LEARNT IN SUMEX

The process behind the **formation of the CoP** was built as a thorough and well thought out process. One notable challenge that was encountered was the difficulty in initiating and sustaining discussions and postings within the CoP. Although many members read and liked the posts, getting them to actively engage proved to be a challenge. In response, a plan was devised to encourage both consortium members and advisory board members to contribute by posting issues related to our focus areas and more.

In terms of the CoP's participation in regional workshops, strategies were outlined for recruitment and engagement, particularly in physical events. The approach involves organizing dynamic and diverse events, including site visits, working groups, presentations of good practice cases, panel discussions, and ample breaks for informal networking and discussions. This was also applicable to digital events and proved useful to keep the engagement during events. Furthermore, leveraging the project's diverse network of partners and utilizing personal contacts and invitations, especially when attendees are acquainted with each other, enhances awareness and participation in these workshops, events, and courses.

Regarding the **actions related to the 3L approach** and their appropriateness for awareness raising, learning, and training, it was found that notably, LinkedIn postings and paid campaigns emerged as the most effective means for increasing awareness and engaging individuals in SUMEX actions. This platform proved to be highly impactful in both aspects.

In terms of the **specifics related to content variations**, with a spin on SUMEX FAs and the feasibility of learning about the respective topics, it was found that the employed approach of using an online course format, albeit it being necessary by the COVID-19 crisis and the switch to digital formats, proved to be a good and sustainable decision. The project was able to use the established platforms network and to expand the outreach of the MOOC and thus also its project work in addition to attracting people from within the project's networks. The digital nature of the course is also a necessary requirement for it to be transferred and used after project end, more on this in the last chapter.

The blend of text materials, examples sourced from the repository, real-time interaction on discussion forums, expert videos, and quizzes, worked effectively to engage the CoP. This combination allowed for a comprehensive learning experience. While the online format proved valuable for learning, it doesn't entirely replicate the hands-on aspects of real-life interactions and practical exposure.

During the promotion of the project's activities, it proved to be of crucial value to professionally promote and communicate the project's activities. This ensured an established information and communication exchange within the CoP and expanded the outreach of the project.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS IN PEER LEARNING AND TRAINING SETTINGS

Based on the learnings experienced during the course of the project, the following points are recommended:

- **Topical relevance and relatedness to the world of policy and industry practitioners:** It is crucial to ensure that the relevance of the topic context, in the context of the SUMEX project the five focus areas, is preserved throughout the learning and engagement process. This helps participants to stay focused and connected to the core subject matter.
- **Encouraging continuous interaction among participants:** This can be achieved through both online platforms and in-person events, fostering ongoing discussions and collaborations.
- **Create a moderated and respectful setting:** Utilise Code of Conducts, Chatham House rule explanations and organised and thoughtful moderation and facilitation in both online and in-person exchange formats.
- **Different learning formats benefit from different expert engagement:** The Background and institutional origin of participants might vary according to the learning setting: making clear the purpose of the learning exercise (peer-to-peer learning I.e. SUMEX regional Workshops versus broad introduction to a topic I.e. SUMEX MOOC). Ex-ante Understanding and clarifying the expectations and experience of other stakeholder groups within the same field was highlighted as a learning outcome.
- **Pre-structure content and major lines of discussions:** Online environments are very succinct and to the point to enable very fast learning outcomes and cope with the fact the attention time frames are quite limited: Having shorter information snippets in the form of videos and short, but very practical and illustrative examples, helps to accommodate this challenge. Pre-defined topics and questions is a very good idea to facilitate discussion as time is quite limited and a large number of questions may also lead to 'fast and general' discussions rather than in-depth ones.
- **Coherent and harmonised approach** of good practice relevant information needs to be put into context and communicated in a "story-based" structure (I.e. SUMEX case studies in Sweden and Spain highlighting key aspects, introduction/background, actors involved etc.) to allow for a good understanding and, ultimately, transfer of good practice into other institutions and countries etc.
- **Leveraging state-of-the-art information** and a repository of resources to ensure that learning environments are enriched with the latest and scientifically sound content. Regular updates are essential to keep the material relevant.
- **Employing modern and easily digestible media formats** to make learning engaging and accessible. These formats should be complemented by opportunities for personal exchanges, both online and in physical gatherings.
- **Facilitate a general level of technical understanding:** Some participants who have not been involved in the SUMEX project need to make sense of the results (i.e. avoidance of project language and technical terminology without any further explanation). It is necessary to ensure that learning materials and discussions use a common language and simplify technical terminology where required. This approach will make the content more inclusive and comprehensible for a diverse audience.
- **Group fun and educational activities foster team spirit and informal exchange settings:** The organisation of physical events that include site visits shows the application potential of the project's research outputs. These events can serve as opportunities to bring together stakeholders from various interest groups, such as civil society, policymakers, and industry representatives. This diversity of perspectives can enrich the learning experience.
- **Language accessibility:** While it's important to consider providing training materials in participants' mother tongues, this should be carefully evaluated based on the specific needs and preferences of the audience. Offering materials in multiple languages may enhance accessibility.

- **Post-project and future oriented project outputs:** The digital nature of the toolkit enabled the incorporation of a post-project perspective into the education process. It is important to develop strategies for handing over and maintaining established courses, materials, and resources to ensure their longevity, especially in the context of time-limited projects.

6.3 NEXT STEPS: EIT ACADEMY FOR MOOC & COP CONTINUATION

Using LinkedIn, the pre-eminent professional social media platform, as the host platform for the SUMEX CoP proved to be a good decision, as it ensures that the CoP will continue after the end of the project. For this, two things will happen:

- The SUMEX team will hand over the administration of the CoP to the Horizon project CIRAN (working on the link between mineral extraction and environmentally sensitive areas), which in its scope also has the establishment of a CoP. Rather than building one from scratch, they will build on the SUMEX CoP, creating a beneficial outcome for both projects. In fact, it is planned to open the CoP also for other EU projects with extractive and sustainability related scopes, thus not only ensuring the continuation of the SUMEX CoP, but also creating clustering and exchange possibilities between projects.
- The CoP will be renamed to “Sustainable Management in the Extractive Sector – navigating challenges and forging new paths” on LinkedIn in order to better allow for the opening up of the CoP and make it independent of the (finished) SUMEX project.

The SUMEX Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) has been highly successful in engaging the community and disseminating information. As a result, it will be continued and transferred to the EIT Raw Materials Academy on the Future Learn platform, starting from November 2023. The EIT Raw Materials Academy hosts specialized courses that align well thematically with the MOOC, ensuring accessibility for both existing and new learners in the future. The course content has been designed to remain relevant beyond the project's duration, making it applicable in various contexts.

The SUMEX website, which serves as an essential information hub, will also be maintained, updated, and available for five years following the conclusion of the project. The knowledge repository will similarly be kept up to date and reviewed after the project's conclusion, ensuring the continued availability of valuable resources.

SUMEX PROJECT BACKGROUND

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC that started on 01.11.2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*Sustainable Management in Extractive industries*) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration-to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify stakeholder learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all stakeholders.

More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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